

INVERSE PROBLEM FOR FRACTIONAL ORDER SUBDIFFUSION EQUATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19245486>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 11-mart 2026 yil

Ma'qullandi: 14-mart 2026 yil

Nashr qilindi: 27-mart 2026 yil

KEY WORDS

subdiffusion equation,
inverse problem, the Caputo
derivatives, the Fourier method.

ABSTRACT

This paper is devoted to an inverse source problem for a time-fractional Subdiffusion equation with the Caputo derivative in a Hilbert space. The elliptic part of the equation is represented by a self-adjoint positive operator A with a discrete spectrum. The right-hand side has the separated form $g(t)f$, where the function $g(t)$ is known, while the element $f \in H$ must be determined. As additional information, we employ the general weighted integral condition $\int_0^T \mu(t)u(t) dt = \psi$, where $\mu(t)$ is a given scalar function and $\psi \in H$ is prescribed. A criterion for the uniqueness of a solution to the inverse problem is found.

MSC (2020): Primary 35R11; Secondary 34A12.

Introduction

Suppose that H is a separable Hilbert space with scalar product (\cdot, \cdot) , and let A be a linear operator in H with domain $D(A)$ satisfying the following assumptions:

- $A = A^*$, where A^* denotes the adjoint operator of A ;
- $(Ah, h) \geq \lambda_0(h, h)$ for all $h \in D(A)$, with some $\lambda_0 > 0$.

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Assume further that the operator A possesses a complete orthonormal system of eigenfunctions $\{v_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty} \subset H$ corresponding to a countable set of strictly positive eigenvalues $\{\lambda_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$. Without loss of generality, we assume that the eigenvalues are ordered as

$$\lambda_0 \leq \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Then each element $h \in D(A)$ admits the Fourier representation

$$Ah = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k h_k v_k, \quad h_k = (h, v_k).$$

Consequently, the domain of the operator A has the form

$$D(A) = \{h \in H: \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 |h_k|^2 < \infty\}.$$

On $D(A)$ we introduce the scalar product

$$(h, g)_1 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 h_k \overline{g_k} = (Ah, Ag), \quad h, g \in D(A),$$

with the induced norm $\|h\|_1^2 = (h, h)_1$. With this norm the space $D(A)$ becomes a Hilbert space.

Let $C((a, b); H)$ denote the space of continuous H -valued functions on (a, b) .

Caputo fractional derivative. For a function $y(t)$ defined on $[0, \infty)$, the Caputo fractional derivative of order $0 < \rho < 1$ is defined (see [1], p. 14) by

$$D_t^\rho y(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\rho)} \int_0^t \frac{y'(\xi)}{(t-\xi)^\rho} d\xi, \quad t > 0,$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ denotes Euler's gamma function.

Inverse problem I. Find a pair $\{u(t), f\}$ satisfying the subdiffusion equation

$$D_t^\rho u(t) + Au(t) = g(t)f, \quad t \in (0, T], \quad (1)$$

with the initial condition

$$u(0) = \varphi, \quad (2)$$

and the weighted integral condition

$$\int_0^T \mu(t)u(t) dt = \psi. \quad (3)$$

Here $g(t), \mu(t) \in C[0, T]$ are given scalar functions, and $\varphi, \psi \in H$ are prescribed elements.

In solving the inverse problem, we will investigate the Cauchy problem for various differential equations. By the solution of the problem, we mean the classical solution, that is, we assume that all the derivatives and functions involved in the equation are continuous with respect to the variable t . As an example, we give the definition of the solution of Inverse problem I.

Definition 1. A pair of function $u(t) \in AC([0, T]; H)$ and $f \in H$ with properties $D_t^\rho u(t), Au(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ satisfying conditions (1)-(2) is called **the solution** of the inverse problem.

Recently, inverse problems related to integer or fractional order differential equations have received more attention among researchers (see monograph [2] and handbook [3]).

Most research on a source function determination focuses on specific processes such as $F = g(t)f(x)$, where either $g(t)$ or $f(x)$ is unknown. Inverse problems of finding the function $g(t)$ have been studied, for example, in [4]-[5]. When $f(x)$ is unknown and $g(t) \equiv 1$, the corresponding inverse problems have been studied by many authors (see [6]-[12]). In the present, we focus on the problem of determining the function $f(x)$, when $g(t) \equiv 1$. Similar problems for the diffusion equation are

studied in the fundamental monograph of S.Kabanikhin [2] and the papers [13]-[19]. As for the subdiffusion equation, such inverse problems are studied in papers[20]-[23].

In the paper [23], researchers analyzed the subdiffusion equation with the Caputo derivative, in which the Laplace operator forms the elliptic part of the equation. The work focused on forward and inverse problems for the subdiffusion equation. In the inverse problem, to find the unknown function $f(x)$ the authors consider the equality $u(x, t_0) = \psi$ as an additional condition. If the function $g(t)$ is sign-preserving, then the authors proved the uniqueness and existence of the solution to the inverse problem. Moreover, in the case where the function $g(t)$ changes sign, a necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a classical solution was found. It should be noted that all the findings presented in this paper for the case where $g(t)$ changes its sign are also new for the classical diffusion equation. In the present paper, we will utilize some ideas from this work to solve Inverse problem I.

The present paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we mention some properties of Mittag-Leffler functions. Section 3 is dedicated to the study of Inverse problem I, and the necessary lemma is proved. In Section 4, we introduce the main result and its proof.

Preliminaries

Let us remind some properties of the Mittag-Leffler function.

For $0 < \rho < 1$ and an arbitrary complex number μ , let $E_{\rho, \mu}(z)$ denote the Mittag-Leffler function with two parameters of the complex argument z (see [24], p. 133):

$$E_{\rho, \mu}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\rho k + \mu)}.$$

Lemma 1 (see [24], p. 136). For any $t \geq 0$ one has

$$|E_{\rho, \mu}(-t)| \leq \frac{C}{1+t}, \quad \rho > 0, \quad \mu \in \mathbb{C}.$$

where constant C does not depend on t and μ .

Lemma 2 [see [25], p. 47] The classical Mittag-Leffler function of the negative argument $E_{\rho}(-t)$ is monotonically decreasing function for all $0 < \rho < 1$ and

$$0 < E_{\rho}(-t) < 1, \quad E_{\rho}(0) = 1.$$

Lemma 3 (see [24], p. 134). Let $0 < \rho < 1$ and μ be an arbitrary complex number. Then the following asymptotic estimate holds

$$E_{\rho, \mu}(-t) = -\sum_{k=1}^2 \frac{(-t)^{-k}}{\Gamma(\mu - k\rho)} + O(t^{-3}), \quad t \rightarrow \infty.$$

Lemma 4 (see [25], p. 61). For all positive t one has

$$\int_0^t \eta^{\beta-1} E_{\rho, \beta}(\lambda \eta^{\rho}) d\eta = t^{\beta} E_{\rho, \beta+1}(\lambda t^{\rho}), \quad \rho > 0, \quad \beta > 0, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{C}.$$

The solution of Inverse problem I

The problem of determining the function $u(t)$ that satisfies the subdiffusion equation (1) together with the initial condition (2) will be referred to as the *forward problem*. This problem has been extensively studied in the literature, and the existence and the uniqueness of its solution have been established in work, including [26]. These results provide the analytical foundation for investigating the corresponding inverse problem.

To solve the Inverse problem I, we employ the following representation of the solution to the forward problem (see [26]):

If $\varphi, f \in H$ and $g(t) \in C[0, T]$, then the forward problem admits a unique solution of the form

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [\varphi_k E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) + f_k b_k(t)] v_k, \quad (4)$$

where $\varphi_k = (\varphi, v_k)$, $f_k = (f, v_k)$, and

$$b_k(t) = \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta.$$

To determine the unknown pair $\{u(t), f\}$ in the Inverse problem I, we substitute the representation (4) into the additional condition (2). This yields

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [\varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt + f_k \int_0^T \mu(t) \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta dt] v_k = \psi.$$

Passing to the Fourier coefficients of both sides, we obtain

$$f_k I_k(T) = \psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt, \quad (5)$$

where

$$I_k(T) = \int_0^T \mu(t) \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta dt.$$

When finding a solution of the inverse problem using the Fourier method, the quantity $I_k(T)$ is involved in the denominator. Therefore, we need a lower bound for $I_k(T)$. Let us consider the case when $g(t)$ and $\mu(t)$ are either negative or positive at the same time. Then the following lemma holds.

Lemma 5 Let $\rho \in (0,1]$, $g(t) \in C[0, T]$, $g(t) \neq 0$, $t \in [0, T]$ and $\mu(t) \in C[0, T]$, $\mu(t) \neq 0$, $t \in [0, T]$. Then there is constant $C_0 > 0$, depending on T , such that for all k one has:

$$|I_k(T)| \geq \frac{C_0}{\lambda_k}.$$

Proof. By virtue of the Weierstrass theorem, we have $|g(t)| \geq g_0 = \text{const} > 0$ and $|\mu(t)| \geq \mu_0 = \text{const} > 0$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} I_k(T) &= \int_0^T \mu(t) \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta dt \\ &\geq \mu_0 \int_0^T \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta dt. \end{aligned}$$

According to this equation (see [27], Lemma 2.4)

$$\int_0^T \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta dt = \int_0^T (T-\eta)^\rho E_{\rho,\rho+1}(-\lambda_k(T-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta,$$

we have

$$I_k(T) \geq \mu_0 \int_0^T (T-\eta)^\rho E_{\rho,\rho+1}(-\lambda_k(T-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta \geq \mu_0 g_0 \int_0^T (T-\eta)^\rho E_{\rho,\rho+1}(-\lambda_k(T-\eta)^\rho) d\eta.$$

Due to Lemmas 1 and 4 we have

$$I_k(T) \geq \frac{C_0}{\lambda_k}.$$

In this section, we will formulate the main results of the work.

Theorem 1. Let $\rho \in (0,1)$, $\varphi \in H$, $\psi \in D(A)$. Further, we will assume that the conditions of Lemma 5 are satisfied. Then there exists a unique solution of Inverse problem I:

$$f = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt] v_k,$$

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [\varphi_k E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) + \frac{b_k(t)}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt]] v_k.$$

Proof. First, we refer to equation (5). Since $I_k(T) \neq 0$ for all $k \in \mathbf{N}$, then from equation (5) we get:

$$f_k = \frac{1}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt].$$

With these Fourier coefficients we have the formal series for unknown element f :

$$f = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt] v_k. \quad (6)$$

Let us prove the convergence of series (6). Denote by F_j the partial sum of series (6):

$$F_j = \sum_{k=1}^j \frac{1}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt] v_k = F_{j,1} + F_{j,2}.$$

First, we estimate the sum $F_{j,1}$. For this, applying Parseval's equality, we arrive at:

$$\|F_{j,1}\|^2 = \|\sum_{k=1}^j \frac{\psi_k}{I_k(T)} v_k\|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^j \frac{1}{|I_k(T)|^2} |\psi_k|^2 \leq C \|\psi\|_1^2.$$

Now, let us estimate the sum $F_{j,2}$. According to Parseval's equality and Lemma 1, we have:

$$\|F_{j,2}\|^2 = \|\sum_{k=1}^j \frac{\varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt}{I_k(T)} v_k\|^2 \leq \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mu(t)|^2 \sum_{k=1}^j \left| \frac{E_{\rho,2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho)}{I_k(T)} \right|^2 |\varphi_k|^2 \leq C \|\varphi\|^2.$$

Thus, if $\varphi \in H$, $\psi \in D(A)$, then from estimates of $F_{j,1}$ we obtain $f \in H$.

After finding the unknown function $f \in H$, we obtain the following formal solution for function $u(t)$:

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\varphi_k E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) + \frac{b_k(t)}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt] \right] v_k. \quad (7)$$

From this equality, we have the following form for Fourier coefficients $u_k(t)$ of function $u(t)$:

$$u_k(t) = \varphi_k E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) + \frac{b_k(t)}{I_k(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt].$$

Now we need to show that function $u(t)$ is a solution of Inverse problem I. If $S_j(t)$ is the partial sums of series (7), then by virtue of the Parseval equality we may write

$$\|AS_j(t)\|^2 = \sum_{k=1}^j |S_{j,1} + S_{j,2}|^2 \leq 2 \sum_{k=1}^j S_{j,1}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^j S_{j,2}^2 = 2I_{j,1} + 2I_{j,2},$$

where

$$S_{j,1} = \lambda_k \varphi_k \frac{I_k(T) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) - b_k(t) \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt}{I_k(T)},$$

and

$$S_{j,2} = \lambda_k \psi_k \frac{b_k(t)}{I_k(T)}.$$

Apply Lemma 5 to obtain

$$I_{j,1} \leq C \sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k^4 |\varphi_k|^2 \left| I_k(T) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) - b_k(t) \int_0^T \mu(t) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) dt \right|^2$$

(according to Lemmas 1 and 4)

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq C \sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k^4 |\varphi_k|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |g(t)|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mu(t)|^2 \left[(T^{\rho+1} E_{\rho,\rho+2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho) E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho))^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (t^\rho T E_{\rho,2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho) E_{\rho,\rho+1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho))^2 \right] \\ &\leq C \sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k^4 |\varphi_k|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |g(t)|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mu(t)|^2 \left[\left(\frac{T^{\rho+1}}{(1+\lambda_k t^\rho)(1+\lambda_k T^\rho)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{T t^\rho}{(1+\lambda_k T^\rho)(1+\lambda_k t^\rho)} \right)^2 \right] \\ &\leq CT(t^{-\rho} + T^{-\rho}) \|\varphi\|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |g(t)|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mu(t)|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Due to Lemmas 4 and 5, we get

$$I_{j,2} \leq C \sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k^4 |\psi_k|^2 |b_k(t)|^2 \leq C \sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k^4 |\psi_k|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |g(t)|^2 t^{2\rho} (E_{\rho,\rho+1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho))^2.$$

Next, we apply Lemma 1 and we have

$$I_{j,2} \leq C \sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k^4 |\psi_k|^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |g(t)|^2 \left[\frac{t^\rho}{1+\lambda_k t^\rho} \right]^2 \leq C \|\psi\|_1^2 \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |g(t)|^2.$$

Hence $Au(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ and in particular $u(t) \in C([0, T]; H)$. Further, from equation (1) one has $D_t^\rho S_j(t) = -AS_j(t) + \sum_{k=1}^j f_k g(t) v_k$, $t > 0$. Therefore, from the above reasoning, we have $D_t^\rho u(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$.

To prove the uniqueness of the solution, assume the opposite, that is, there are two different solutions $\{u_1, f_1\}$ and $\{u_2, f_2\}$ satisfying Inverse problem I. We must show that $u \equiv u_1 - u_2 \equiv 0$, $f \equiv f_1 - f_2 \equiv 0$. For $\{u, f\}$ we get the problem:

$$D_t^\rho u(t) + Au(t) = g(t)f, \quad t \in (0, T],$$

(initial condition)

$$u(0) = 0,$$

(additional condition)

$$\int_0^T u(t) dt = 0.$$

Let us take any solution $\{u, f\}$ and define $u_k = (u, v_k)$ and $f_k = (f, v_k)$. Then, according to the self-adjointness of operator A , we obtain

$$D_t^\rho u_k(t) = (D_t^\rho u, v_k) = -(Au, v_k) + f_k g(t) = -(u, Av_k) + f_k g(t) = -\lambda_k u_k(t) + f_k g(t).$$

Therefore, for u_k we get the Cauchy problem

$$D_t^\rho u_k(t) + \lambda_k u_k(t) = f_k g(t), \quad t > 0, \quad u_k(0) = 0,$$

and the additional condition

$$\int_0^T u_k(t)dt = 0.$$

If f_k is known, then the unique solution of the Cauchy problem has the form

$$u_k(t) = f_k \int_0^t \eta^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k \eta^\rho) g(t-\eta) d\eta. \quad (8)$$

Apply the additional condition to equation (8) to have

$$\int_0^T u_k(t)dt = f_k \int_0^T \mu(t) \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta dt = f_k I_k(T) = 0.$$

Since $I_k(T) \neq 0$ for all $k \in \mathbf{N}$, then due to completeness of the set of eigenfunctions $\{v_k\}$ in H , we finally have $f \equiv 0$ and $u(t) \equiv 0$.

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